

A MICROMECHANICS BASED CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

Van D. Vu¹, Abdul H. Sheikh² and Giang Nguyen³

School of Civil, Environmental and Mining Engineering, the University of Adelaide
North Terrace Campus, Adelaide, South Australia, web page: <http://www.adelaide.edu.au/>

¹Email: van.vu@adelaide.edu.au,

²Email: abdul.sheikh@adelaide.edu.au

³Email: g.nguyen@adelaide.edu.au

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new micromechanics-based constitutive model is developed for fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites having unidirectional fibre orientations which can incorporate elastic and inelastic responses of both fibres and matrix. The composite material is idealised by a representative volume element consisting of four material blocks where one of them is for fibre and the others for matrix. Kinematic enrichments of different strain components for the different material blocks are used to accommodate the responses of different material blocks. The model is first used to evaluate orthotropic material properties of composites in the elastic range using isotropic material properties of the constituents. After a successful validation of these predicted material properties using existing theoretical as well as experimental results, the model is applied to inelastic material response to assess its performance in the nonlinear range.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials is becoming popular in many engineering disciplines over the last few decades due to their high specific strength and stiffness, exceptional durability and some other attractive features. The composite structures can be subjected to complex loading conditions such as extreme temperature, dynamic loads, impact, corrosion and some other loading scenarios which will induce complex loading paths on the materials. Moreover, the composite nature of these materials consisting of different dissimilar phases leads to additional complexities. Thus the analysis of composite structures requires a good model that can predict the behaviour of the material properly. This in turn needs an advanced constitutive model which will accurately capture the deformation of the matrix and fibres along with their interactions.

In the literature, a large number of models have been developed by different researchers attempting to capture the responses of these materials correctly. Most of the existing models can be categorised into two distinct branches: macro-mechanical and micro-mechanical models. The initial developments of some popular macro-mechanical models are due to Hoffman, Puck, Hashin and Rotem [1-3] and few others. Tsai [4] also attempted to develop a failure criterion, popularly known as Tsai-Hill theory, for “weak” anisotropic materials. Although these models are easy to use, they are of phenomenological nature that needs a large set of experimental data for their development. As a consequence these models may not be reliable when applied outside the range of these data sets. Macro-mechanical models actually treat the composite material as a single homogeneous material and do not follow the actual deformations and correct failure mechanisms of the constituents and their interactions.

On the other hand, some researchers such as Christensen and Lo, Mori and Tanaka, and Aboudi [5-7] have proposed micromechanics-based models, in which the overall properties of the composites are determined by using a Representative Volume Element (RVE) consist of their constituents. Despite the fact that more realistic results could be obtained by using these micromechanics-based models, most of the earlier ones are not applicable in inelastic range where the constituents will have plastic deformations, damage and their coupling. Besides, thanks to the advances of computing power, full micromechanical analyses of composite materials, where all constituents can be modelled

explicitly, are gradually applicable. This provides us with useful tools for the analysis of composite failure in the inelastic range and can produce results with high levels of accuracy, which seems quite attractive for furthering the understanding of failure mechanisms. However, the computational demand of a full micromechanical model is so high that the use of such model is not feasible for the analysis of a real structure.

In this study, a micromechanics-based constitutive model for unidirectional fibre composite is developed that can be used within a framework of a macro-mechanical analysis. The model inherits the computational efficiency of a macro-mechanical model and at the same time the important physical behaviours and interactions of matrix and fibre are embraced. First, a mathematical derivation of the current model is introduced following by the validation of the model in the elastic range with some existing classical theories as well as experimental results available in literature. The validation of these results covering a wide range of elastic material properties shows a promising performance of the proposed model. The model is then applied in the inelastic range taking nonlinear material response of the constituents and their interactions. The trend of the nonlinear results indicates a good future potential of the model.

2 A MICROMECHANICS BASED CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Figure 1 shows a representative volume element (RVE) which is conceptualised for modelling the behaviours of unidirectional composites aiming to retain essential mechanisms of fibres, matrix and their interactions whilst being simple enough to accommodate inelastic behaviours of different phases. The central idea of this model is to have sufficient lower scale (fibre scale) details for the prediction at higher scales, while minimising the computational demand. In this sense, the deformation of the matrix and the fibre will be modelled distinctly and they will be combined together utilising their interaction to predict the deformation of the composite material. Denoting f as the matrix volume fraction, the corresponding volume fractions of the three matrix blocks (M-1, M-2, M-3), defined as f_1 , f_2 and f_3 respectively, can easily be expressed in terms of f (Figure 1). The homogenised or macro strain rate of the volume element or the composite can be written in matrix-vector form as:

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}\} = f_1\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} + f_2\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} + f_3\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} + (1 - f)\{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} \quad (1)$$

The strain rates (or increments) of the different matrix blocks can be defined in terms of fibre block strain rates with the enhancement of their transverse strain increments as:

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} + [N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} \quad (3)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (4)$$

where the enhancement terms ($\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} = \{\dot{\tilde{\gamma}}_{2xy} \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_{2yy} \dot{\tilde{\gamma}}_{2yz}\}^T$ and $\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} = \{\dot{\tilde{\gamma}}_{3xz} \dot{\tilde{\gamma}}_{3yz} \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_{3zz}\}^T$) appear only in the appropriate positions of the strain vectors which are accommodated with the help of two matrices $[N_2]$ and $[N_3]$ corresponding to the directions (y and z respectively) of the two interfaces (see Appendix for details).

From Equations (1) to (4), we can express the matrix and fibre strain rates in term of the homogenised strain rate and enhanced strain rates as:

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1 + f_2)[N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} - (f_1 + f_3)[N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (5)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_2))[N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_3))[N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (6)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_2))[N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} - (f_1 + f_3)[N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1 + f_2)[N_2]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_3))[N_3]\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\} \quad (8)$$

Figure 1: A Representative Volume Element for unidirectional composites (F: Fibre block; M-1, M-2, M-3: Matrix blocks).

The enhanced strain rates can be eliminated from the above equations which will help to express the matrix and fibre strain rates in term of homogenised strain rates and volume fractions. Now the Hill-Mandel condition of virtual work [8] can be used as:

$$\{\sigma\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}\} = f_1 \{\sigma_{m1}\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} + f_2 \{\sigma_{m2}\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} + f_3 \{\sigma_{m3}\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} + (1-f) \{\sigma_f\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} \quad (9)$$

Substitution of the segmental strain rates as expressed in Equations (5) to (8) into the above equation (9), it can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\sigma\}^T \{\dot{\epsilon}\} = & f_1 \{\sigma_{m1}\}^T (\{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_2] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_3] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\}) \\ & + f_2 \{\sigma_{m2}\}^T (\{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_2] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} - (f_1 + f_3) [N_3] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\}) \\ & + f_3 \{\sigma_{m3}\}^T (\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1 + f_2) [N_2] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} + (1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_3] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\}) \\ & + (1-f) \{\sigma_f\}^T (\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1 + f_2) [N_2] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\} - (f_1 + f_3) [N_3] \{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The above equation will be valid for any arbitrary values of these strain rates $\{\dot{\epsilon}_f\}$, $\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_2\}$, and $\{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_3\}$ if the following conditions are satisfied:

$$\{\sigma\} = f_1 \{\sigma_{m1}\} + f_2 \{\sigma_{m2}\} + f_3 \{\sigma_{m3}\} + (1-f) \{\sigma_f\} \quad (11)$$

$$f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) \{\sigma_{m1}\}^T [N_2] + f_2(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) \{\sigma_{m2}\}^T [N_2] - f_3(f_1 + f_2) \{\sigma_{m3}\}^T [N_2] - (1-f)(f_1 + f_2) \{\sigma_f\}^T [N_2] = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) \{\sigma_{m1}\}^T [N_3] - f_2(f_1 + f_3) \{\sigma_{m2}\}^T [N_3] + f_3(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) \{\sigma_{m3}\}^T [N_3] - (1-f)(f_1 + f_3) \{\sigma_f\}^T [N_3] = 0 \quad (13)$$

Equation (11) gives the homogenised stresses of the whole RVE expressed in terms of stresses of the matrix and fibre and their volume fractions. Equations (12) and (13) enforce average traction continuity across the interfaces 2-2 and 3-3 (Figure 1).

Now denoting $[F]$ and $[M]$ as the tangent stiffness matrix of the fibre and matrix respectively, the stresses rates in the fibre and matrix blocks can be written in generic forms as:

$$\{\dot{\sigma}_f\} = [F] \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} \quad (14)$$

$$\{\dot{\sigma}_{m1}\} = [M_1]\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} \quad (15)$$

$$\{\dot{\sigma}_{m2}\} = [M_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} \quad (16)$$

$$\{\dot{\sigma}_{m3}\} = [M_3]\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} \quad (17)$$

Using Equation (11), the relationship between the homogenised or macro stress rates can be expressed in terms of stress rates of all the material blocks as:

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = f_1\{\dot{\sigma}_{m1}\} + f_2\{\dot{\sigma}_{m2}\} + f_3\{\dot{\sigma}_{m3}\} + (1-f)\{\dot{\sigma}_f\} \quad (18)$$

Moreover, the stress rates in all material blocks are connected through the continuity of traction rates at the interfaces between the fibre and matrix blocks which can be obtained using Equations (12) and (13) as:

$$f_1(1-(f_1+f_2))\{\dot{\sigma}_{m1}\}^T[N_2] + f_2(1-(f_1+f_2))\{\dot{\sigma}_{m2}\}^T[N_2] - f_3(f_1+f_2)\{\dot{\sigma}_{m3}\}^T[N_2] - (1-f)(f_1+f_2)\{\dot{\sigma}_f\}^T[N_2] = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$f_1(1-(f_1+f_3))\{\dot{\sigma}_{m1}\}^T[N_3] - f_2(f_1+f_3)\{\dot{\sigma}_{m2}\}^T[N_3] + f_3(1-(f_1+f_3))\{\dot{\sigma}_{m3}\}^T[N_3] - (1-f)(f_1+f_3)\{\dot{\sigma}_f\}^T[N_3] = 0 \quad (20)$$

Substitution of Equations (5) - (8) and (14) - (17) into Equations (19) and (20), we can obtain:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\dot{\epsilon}_2\} \\ \{\dot{\epsilon}_3\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} \{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (21)$$

which shows that the homogenised strain rates can be determined with the strain enhancements, and the matrices $[A_{11}]$, $[A_{12}]$, $[A_{21}]$, $[A_{22}]$, $[B_1]$ & $[B_2]$ which are dependent on material properties and volume fractions of the matrix and fibres (refer to the Appendix for more details). Now the strain enhancement terms can be expressed in terms of the homogenised strain terms from the above equation as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{\dot{\epsilon}_2\} \\ \{\dot{\epsilon}_3\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} \{\dot{\epsilon}\} = \begin{bmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \end{bmatrix} \{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (22)$$

Using Equations (5) to (8) and (22), the strain rates in the matrix and fibre blocks can be completely defined by the homogenised strain rate as:

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1-(f_1+f_2))[N_2][P_1]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1-(f_1+f_3))[N_3][P_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (23)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (1-(f_1+f_2))[N_2][P_1]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1+f_3)[N_3][P_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (24)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} + (f_1+f_2)[N_2][P_1]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (1-(f_1+f_3))[N_3][P_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (25)$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1+f_2)[N_2][P_1]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - (f_1+f_3)[N_3][P_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (26)$$

Substituting these strain rate expressions (23-26) into the volume averaged stress rate relationship (18), the constitutive relationship for the homogenised/macro stress and strain can finally be obtained in rate form as:

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = [C]\{\dot{\epsilon}\} \quad (27)$$

where

$$[C] = f_1[M_1] + f_2[M_2] + f_3[M_3] + (1-f)[F] + (f_1-f_1(f_1+f_2))[M_1][N_2][P_1] + (f_1-f_1(f_1+f_3))[M_1][N_3][P_2] + (f_2-f_2(f_1+f_2))[M_2][N_2][P_1] - f_2(f_1 + \quad (28)$$

$$f_3)[M_2][N_3][P_2] - f_3(f_1 + f_2)[M_3][N_2][P_1] + (f_3 - f_3(f_1 + f_3))[M_3][N_3][P_2] - (1 - f)(f_1 + f_2)[F][N_2][P_1] - (1 - f)(f_1 + f_3)[F][N_3][P_2]$$

The above equation shows that the rate form of the constitutive matrix of the homogenised composite material is explicitly defined in terms of constitutive matrices (in rate form) of the constituents and their volume fractions. Thus the model does not have any restriction in its application in the elastic as well as inelastic ranges. In principle, the macro-mechanical strain rates at an integration point of an element within a structure can be resolved into strain rates of the fibre and matrix blocks (Fig. 1). With these strain rates, the stresses in each block can be calculated following standard stress return algorithms (see [9]). The homogenised stress can then be obtained from Equation (11). Further details can be found in [10].

3 INELASTIC ANALYSIS

As mentioned in the previous section, the formulation can be readily extended to inelastic/nonlinear range. To test the ability of the model in predicting constitutive behaviours of metal matrix composite, the material blocks in this study are assumed to follow Von Mises plasticity model. The stress-strain relationship can be described as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(\varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ij}^p) \quad (29)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the elastic tangent stiffness tensor, ε_{ij}^p represents the plastic strain tensor and ε_{ij} is the total strain tensor comprising elastic and plastic strains.

According to von Mises plasticity theory, the yield function may be written as:

$$y = f(\varepsilon_p) = \sigma_e - k \quad (30)$$

with associated flow rule:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial y}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \quad (31)$$

The effective stress σ_e and effective plastic strain ε_p used in the above equations can be defined as:

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{3J_2} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} s_{ij} s_{ij}} \quad (32)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p} = d\lambda \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial y}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \frac{\partial y}{\partial \sigma_{ij}}} \quad (33)$$

The term k used in Equation (30) corresponds to instantaneous yield stress for an uniaxially loaded member which represents hardening or softening process and it is a function of effective plastic strain ε_p . This yield stress for a linear hardening/softening case may be expressed as:

$$k = \sigma_y + H\varepsilon_p \quad (34)$$

For nonlinear hardening/softening case, it can be expressed as:

$$k = \sigma_y + Q(1 - e^{-b\varepsilon_p}) \quad (35)$$

where H is the hardening or softening rate with respect to plastic strain; Q is the difference between initial yielding stress and ultimate stress; and b is another material property that controls the hardening or softening for the nonlinear case. The choice of these material constants dictates the behaviours of the material blocks of interest.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section is dedicated to the verification of the proposed micromechanics based model in both elastic and inelastic range. Initially the elastic stiffness parameters of unidirectional FRC are predicted by the proposed model and these results are validated with existing theoretical and experimental results for various fibre volume fractions. The proposed model is then examined for its ability to capture the inelastic responses of unidirectional FRC with both hardening and softening behaviours.

4.1 Elastic Properties

4.1.1 Longitudinal Elastic Modulus:

Figure 2 shows the prediction of longitudinal modulus E_l of a composite material (refer to Table 1 for materials properties of the constituents) with respect to fibre volume fractions. The model predictions follow the upper bound solution according to rule of mix or Voigt model. This corresponds to the condition of equal strains within the constituents and it is nicely simulated by the proposed model as it does not have strain enhancement in the longitudinal direction. This behaviour is commonly considered appropriate in the literature.

Engineering constant		Matrix	Fibre
E	[GPa]	5.35	113.4
ν	–	0.22	0.35

Table 1: Material Properties obtained from [11].

Figure 2: Longitudinal Young modulus E_l – (other results obtained from [11]).

4.1.2 Transverse Elastic Modulus (E_2 and E_3):

In a similar manner, the variation of transverse modulus predicted by the proposed model is presented in Figure 3 which is found to deviate from the lower bound solution (Reuss model). According to the rule of mixture, the transverse modulus should follow the lower bound solution which corresponds to the condition of equal stress within the constituents. However, the real test data indicates that the value of transverse modulus should be higher than the lower bound solution and definitely lower than the upper bound solution. Actually, the lower bound solution is based on an assumption that the transverse normal stress within the entire volume of the matrix in the RVE is equal to that of the fibre which follows the concept of springs-in-series. However, this assumption is not valid in reality as only a portion of the matrix volume behaves according to this concept. The current model is based on more realistic assumptions and according to these, the loading in a transverse direction, e.g., direction 2 will allow only matrix blocks M-1 and M-2 to have same transverse normal stresses (σ_{22}^{m1} and σ_{22}^{m2}) as that of fibre block (σ_{22}^f). On the other hand, the transverse

normal strain of M-3 (ϵ_{22}^{m3}) will be equal to that of fibre (ϵ_{22}^f) that will produce different stress within these two blocks as they are having different stiffness of material properties. The present results are also found to closely follows the trend of other theoretical models such as Mori-Tanaka[6], upper bound of Concentric Cylinder Assemblage (CCA+)[12] or Self-Consistent[13] (Figure 3). A similar behaviour is also found for loading in transverse direction 3 and in-plane shearing.

Figure 3: Transverse modulus E_2 – (other results obtained from [11]). Material properties are given in Table 1.

The transverse modulus E_2 or E_3 predicted by the current model for different fibre volume fractions are found to be marginally higher than the upper bound solution of [12](Figure 3). It should be noted that the concept of Hashin’s upper bound solution is different from that of rule of mixture. Actually, Hashin’s model is based on two hypotheses: (i) maximum potential energy and (ii) maximum elastic compliance energy, which results in two distinct bounds for a single material parameter such as transverse modulus. This is a little confusing as this model does not provide a unique value of a modulus. In that sense, the present model is consistent as it predicts a single solution.

The transverse modulus predicted by the current model is also validated against experimental results, as shown in Figure 4 where the material properties used for the constituents are given in Table 2.

Figure 4: Transverse modulus E_2 and in-plane shear modulus G_{12} and G_{23} (other results and experimental data obtained from [14]) – Material properties are given in Table 2.

Engineering constant		Matrix	Fibre
E	[GPa]	4.14	414
ν	–	0.35	0.2

Table 2: Material Properties obtained from [14].

4.1.3 In-plane Shear Modulus

The variation of in-plane shear modulus G_{12} and G_{13} predicted by the proposed model is plotted in Figure 5 along with that obtained by other theories such as Mori-Tanaka[6], Method of Cells (MOCTI)[7] and Self-Consistent[13]. The results in Figure 5 show good correlation with those predicted by most of existing theories. The present results are also validated against the experimental data in Figure 6 which show good agreement between them. In this case, the properties of fibre and matrix are given in Table 3.

Figure 5: In-plane Shear modulus G_{12} & G_{23} - (other results obtained from [11]). Material properties are given in Table 1.

Figure 6: In-plane shear modulus G_{12} and G_{23} for fibre volume fraction from 0.45 to 0.75 (other results obtained from [14]) - Material properties are given in Table 3.

Engineering constant		Matrix	Fibre
G	[GPa]	1.83	30.19
E (Calculated)	[GPa]	5.35	113.4
ν (Calculated)	–	0.22	0.35

Table 3: Material Properties obtained from [14].

4.1.4 Transverse Shear Modulus

The transverse shear modulus G_{23} predicted by the current model is presented in Figure 7 along with that obtained from other theories. The values of G_{23} are less than in-plane shear modulus and closer to the lower bound solution of rule of mix (Figure 7). The predicted values of G_{23} are consistent with the typical properties of unidirectional lamina having isotropic constituents according to [11] i.e., the transverse shear modulus are slightly less than the in-plan shear modulus for the same fibre volume fraction.

Figure 7: Shear modulus G_{12} & G_{23} - other results obtained from [11]. Material properties are given in Table 1.

4.2 Inelastic Response

Examples of plastic behaviours at constitutive level are given in this section. Table 4 & Table 5 below provide the model parameters used for the four materials behaviours in the study. In all four cases simulations were carried out under uniaxial tension along fibre direction for matrix volume fraction of 0.38. Different softening behaviours of the constituents are employed. We note that this is only a preliminary analysis to demonstrate the behaviour of the proposed composite model in inelastic range. More advanced constitutive models for the constituents are being developed and further analyses will be carried out and presented in the future.

Engineering constant		Matrix	Fibre
E	[GPa]	4.14	414
ν	–	0.35	0.2
σ_y	[GPa]	0.03	0.8

Table 4: Material Properties in both hardening and softening cases.

As illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 9 the proposed constitutive model has the ability to capture stress-strain curve of the homogenised RVE while keeping track of the behaviours in the material constituents. In other words, the constituent behaviours are homogenised in every step of calculation to obtain the macro behaviour, following the steps described above. This allows both elastic and inelastic behaviours for the constituents.

The responses of all four material blocks (refer to previous sections) are governed by parameters of the Von Mises model. They in turn control the overall constitutive behaviour of the homogenised composite model. As anticipated, under uniaxial loading in the fibre direction the overall behaviours of the composite is substantially influenced by the responses of fibres which are expected to have major impacts to the overall material stiffness in this loading condition (Figs. 8 & 9). On the other hands, in this uniaxial condition, due to significantly low stiffness of matrix compared to fibres, the contribution of matrix to the overall stiffness of the material is negligible. The softening behaviour in this case is encountered in all constituents. While the fibre behaviour is distinguished, all three matrix blocks behave only slightly differently in this case. These blocks in general response differently due to difference in their input strain rates [10].

Case	Engineering constant		Matrix	Fibre
Linear Hardening	H	–	5	20
Linear Softening	H	–	-0.5	-5
Non-linear Hardening	Q	[GPa]	0.08	1
	b	–	40	100
Non-linear Softening	Q	[GPa]	-0.08	-1
	b	–	20	50

Table 5: Model parameters.

Figure 8: Stress-strain curve for linear strain hardening and softening materials.

Figure 9: Stress-strain curve for nonlinear strain hardening and softening materials.

5 CONCLUSION

The current micromechanics based model has shown very good potentials through their predictions of elastic properties comparable to those by classical theories and experimental results, while possessing capability to handle material nonlinearity. In particular, the enhancements through kinematic terms in this case lead to a mix upper-lower bound solution that in turn result in effective properties close to classical predictions. The embedded fibre and matrix phases are interacting with each other and together control the response of the composite material model. Thanks to the rate form of the whole formulation, any constitutive behaviour can be used for the matrix and fibre. This is the key advantages in further extending the model capability to nonlinear cases with the development and incorporating more capable constitutive behaviour for fibre and matrix.

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APPENDIX

Detailed expressions of enhanced strains and normal matrix $[N_2]$ and $[N_3]$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m2}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xy}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{yz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xz}^f \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{2yy} \\ 0 \\ \dot{\gamma}_{2xy} \\ 0 \\ \dot{\gamma}_{2xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xy}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{yz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xz}^f \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\gamma}_{2xy} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{2yy} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{2yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}_2\}$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m3}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xy}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{yz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xz}^f \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{3zz} \\ 0 \\ \dot{\gamma}_{3yz} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{3xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^f \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xy}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{yz}^f \\ \dot{\gamma}_{xz}^f \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\gamma}_{3xz} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{3yz} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{3zz} \end{Bmatrix} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_3]\{\dot{\epsilon}_3\}$$

$$\{\dot{\epsilon}_{m1}\} = \{\dot{\epsilon}_f\} + [N_2]\{\dot{\epsilon}_2\} + [N_3]\{\dot{\epsilon}_3\}$$

Detailed expressions of matrices in equation (21):

$$[A_{11}] = f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_2))^2 [N_2]^T [M_1] [N_2] + f_2(1 - (f_1 + f_2))^2 [N_2]^T [M_2] [N_2] + f_3(f_1 + f_2)^2 [N_2]^T [M_3] [N_2] + (1 - f)(f_1 + f_2)^2 [N_2]^T [F] [N_2]$$

$$[A_{12}] = f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_2))(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_2]^T [M_1] [N_3] - f_2(1 - (f_1 + f_2))(f_1 + f_3) [N_2]^T [M_2] [N_3] - f_3(f_1 + f_2)(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_2]^T [M_3] [N_3] + (1 - f)(f_1 + f_2)(f_1 + f_3) [N_2]^T [F] [N_3]$$

$$[A_{21}] = f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_3))(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_3]^T [M_1] [N_2] - f_2(f_1 + f_3)(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_3]^T [M_2] [N_2] - f_3(1 - (f_1 + f_3))(f_1 + f_2) [N_3]^T [M_3] [N_2] + (1 - f)(f_1 + f_3)(f_1 + f_2) [N_3]^T [F] [N_2]$$

$$[A_{22}] = f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_3))^2 [N_3]^T [M_1] [N_3] + f_2(f_1 + f_3)^2 [N_3]^T [M_2] [N_3] + f_3(1 - (f_1 + f_3))^2 [N_3]^T [M_3] [N_3] + (1 - f)(f_1 + f_3)^2 [N_3]^T [F] [N_3]$$

$$[B_1] = (1 - f)(f_1 + f_2) [N_2]^T [F] - f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_2]^T [M_1] - f_2(1 - (f_1 + f_2)) [N_2]^T [M_2] + f_3(f_1 + f_2) [N_2]^T [M_3]$$

$$[B_2] = (1 - f)(f_1 + f_3) [N_3]^T [F] - f_1(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_3]^T [M_1] + f_2(f_1 + f_3) [N_3]^T [M_2] - f_3(1 - (f_1 + f_3)) [N_3]^T [M_3]$$